

Additional file 4. List of included articles

- Addy, S., Wilkinson, M.E., 2021. Embankment lowering and natural self-recovery improves river-floodplain hydro-geomorphic connectivity of a gravel bed river. *Sci. Total Environ.* 770.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.144626>
- Ahmad, S., Liu, H., Alam, S., Günther, A., Jurasinski, G., Lennartz, B., 2021. Meteorological Controls on Water Table Dynamics in Fen Peatlands Depend on Management Regimes. *Front. Earth Sci.* 9.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/feart.2021.630469>
- Ahmad, S., Liu, H., Günther, A., Couwenberg, J., Lennartz, B., 2020. Long-term rewetting of degraded peatlands restores hydrological buffer function. *Sci. Total Environ.* 749.
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